

VIEWPOINTS ON CHATGPT USE: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 4

Pages: 411-419

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2676

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14279045

Manuscript Accepted: 11-07-2024

Viewpoints on ChatGPT Use: A Multiple Case Study

Honey Lyn B. Poraso, * Kristy Jane R. Muegna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This multiple case study aimed to explore and determine the viewpoints of teachers on ChatGPT use among students. To gain a comprehensive understanding of teachers' perspectives, experiences, and attitudes regarding the incorporation of ChatGPT, an advanced natural language processing model, in the learning environments of their students. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating nine (9) teachers were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the viewpoints of the participants: absence of academic integrity, potential consequence of promoting students' laziness, contrast between traditional method and modern method of learning, may results to declining of critical thinking skills, and viewing ChatGPT as a supplementary tool. Upon reflecting to their viewpoints, they arrived at the following insights: providing performance-based activities and being responsible in using artificial intelligence. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *teachers' viewpoints, ChatGPT, cross-case analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

ChatGPT, a remarkable embodiment of artificial intelligence and natural language understanding, has emerged as a pioneering force in modern education. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have been progressing constantly and being more visible in different aspects of our lives. One noteworthy development is ChatGPT, a chatbot with a conversational artificial intelligence interface that was developed by OpenAI. However, ChatGPT poses different threats to the traditional education, including the possibility of cheating on online exams, human-like text generation, diminished critical thinking skills, and difficulties in evaluating information generated by ChatGPT. As one of the most advanced artificial intelligence applications, ChatGPT has drawn much public attention across the globe (Tlili et al., 2023).

In New York City, school systems, teachers, and professors fear ChatGPT, viewing it as a potential enabler for widespread academic dishonesty. Recognizing the risk of undermining the integrity of assessments, schools have taken preemptive measures by prohibiting access to ChatGPT—an artificial intelligence bot developed by OpenAI that lets users, including students, ask the tool to write an essay on Shakespeare, solving algebraic equations, or completing coding assignments. Concerns have been raised that the widespread use of OpenAI's chatbot may not only foster a surge in cheating but also have detrimental effects on students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Vincent, 2023).

Meanwhile, in Manila, particularly in the University of the Philippines, many educators fear the program since it threatens academic integrity, encouraging new methods of cheating and plagiarism. Through the program's simplicity, accessibility, and convenience, students have been using it to generate answers to homework and even entire essays, claiming the writing produced by the chatbot as their own. Thus, this follows the spike in the availability of AI-powered chatbots this year, such as ChatGPT, which has stoked worries among educators about widespread cheating and its potential to undermine the learning process (Blose, 2023).

The study is socially relevant because it focuses on teachers' perspectives regarding the integration of ChatGPT into education, acknowledging teachers as the primary architects of lesson plans, instructional strategies, and student assessments. Their insights are crucial for understanding the impact of ChatGPT on teaching methods, classroom dynamics, and student engagement, as well as for identifying areas that may require improvement. The urgency of this study lies in the rapidly evolving educational landscape, where the swift adaptation to emerging technologies like ChatGPT is essential. Teachers feedbacks not only guides the ongoing development and implementation of ChatGPT but also ensures that it meets the evolving needs of classrooms. Furthermore, the findings of this study have the potential to inform evidence-based educational policies, contributing to a comprehensive and informed approach to the utilization of ChatGPT in schools.

In contrast to earlier studies, my research on the viewpoints of teachers on ChatGPT use in learning distinguishes itself through its comprehensive exploration of the technology's long-term efficacy and adaptability across diverse educational contexts. Related studies had been found regarding the phenomenon of ChatGPT such as the study entitled, "ChatGPT for Education and Research: Opportunities, Threats, and Strategies" by Rahman and Watanobe (2023). Also, the study of Kohnke et al. (2023) entitled, "ChatGPT for Language Teaching and Learning". Additionally, the study by Kelly et al. (2023) entitled, "ChatGPT in higher education: Considerations for academic integrity and student learning". The mentioned studies explore the opportunities, challenges, and strategies of using ChatGPT in education and research and identify strategies for potential threats. However, the uniqueness of the current study laid in its specific focus on the teacher's viewpoints from different year levels. This study is different because this focused more on the perceptions of teachers in the use of ChatGPT among students which is still less explored in the body of knowledge. This broader perspective positions my research as a distinctive contribution to the field.

Research Questions

The main objective of this qualitative case study was to explore and determine the viewpoints of teachers on ChatGPT use among students. To achieve this objective, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the unique characteristics of each case?
2. What are the perceptions of teachers in the use of ChatGPT among the students?
3. What are the insights of teachers in the use of ChatGPT among the students?

Literature Review

Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (ChatGPT) and Its Applications

GPT models, particularly ChatGPT, have transformed the landscape of education and research by generating human-like text through extensive pre-training on large datasets (Ray & Zaremba, 2023). While ChatGPT enhances learning opportunities across industries, particularly in education, concerns remain regarding its ethical use. Ausat et al. (2023) highlight that ChatGPT's versatility enables its adoption for varied tasks, but issues related to biases and ethical challenges cannot be ignored. ChatGPT's ability to mimic human language raises questions about authenticity in educational environments, making it crucial for educators to navigate these complexities.

Effects on Academic Performance

While ChatGPT aids students in tasks like generating essays and analyzing data, over-reliance on this tool poses significant challenges. Alneyadi et al. (2023) point out that ChatGPT supports learning in specific domains but caution that students may become dependent on it for completing academic work. Lamas (2018) notes that understanding ChatGPT's impact on academic performance requires teachers and administrators to evaluate both the benefits and drawbacks, ensuring that students continue to develop critical thinking skills despite the presence of such powerful tools.

Mallow (2023) adds that ChatGPT's integration into classrooms must be balanced. While it can enhance learning, it is crucial to avoid fostering dependency. Students should be encouraged to use ChatGPT as a supplement rather than as a substitute for their cognitive processes.

Academic Integrity Concerns

ChatGPT presents a significant challenge to academic integrity, primarily because of its ability to produce content that is difficult to distinguish from human-generated work. Cotton et al. (2024) argue that traditional plagiarism detection tools are struggling to keep up with AI advancements, making it harder to assess student originality. Rahman et al. (2023) concurs, noting that ChatGPT-generated essays or assignments raise serious concerns about the authenticity of student submissions, with students using the AI tool to bypass the learning process. These studies underscore the need for academic institutions to rethink assessment strategies and implement more rigorous integrity safeguards.

Potential for Student Laziness

Teachers have expressed concerns that ChatGPT could lead to a reduction in student effort, fostering laziness. Iqbal et al. (2023) found that students may turn to ChatGPT for quick solutions rather than engaging with the material themselves, which diminishes their cognitive development. Yilmaz and Karaoglan (2023) add that over-reliance on AI tools not only reduces the motivation to solve problems independently but may also cause students to miss out on the deeper learning experiences necessary for long-term success.

Contrasting Traditional and Modern Learning Approaches

The rapid adoption of AI tools like ChatGPT has dramatically shifted the educational landscape. Rahman and Watanobe (2023) argue that traditional methods, which required students to engage in extensive research, have been replaced by AI-generated responses that provide instant solutions. While this has made learning more efficient, it risks limiting students' ability to develop critical thinking and analytical skills. Iqbal et al. (2023) highlight that this transition from traditional learning to AI-assisted learning could reduce the depth of students' engagement with course material, ultimately affecting their academic performance.

Declining Critical Thinking Skills

Maknun (2019) warns that ChatGPT's ability to provide quick answers may lead to a decline in critical thinking and metacognition. Suriano et al. (2024) suggest that educators should design more complex, problem-based tasks that challenge students to think independently. Exintaris et al. (2023) emphasize that students who rely heavily on AI for solutions may struggle to develop the critical thinking skills essential for academic and professional success. The decline in cognitive engagement, if unchecked, could affect students' ability to tackle more complex, real-world problems in the future.

Viewing ChatGPT as a Supplementary Tool

Despite these concerns, many educators recognize the potential benefits of ChatGPT when used appropriately. Shouran (2023) argues that ChatGPT can serve as an effective supplementary tool, particularly for students who need extra help in understanding complex

topics. Wang et al. (2024) stress the importance of critically evaluating AI-generated content, ensuring that students do not rely solely on ChatGPT but use it as one of many learning resources. Ahn and Chen (2020) advocate for integrating AI literacy into curricula, allowing students to navigate AI tools responsibly while understanding their limitations.

Loss of Human Decision-Making

The increased use of AI in education, particularly in decision-making processes, has raised concerns about the diminishing role of human judgment. (Abbas et al., 2022) and (Javaid et al., 2023) caution that the reliance on AI for tasks previously managed by teachers and administrators could erode essential cognitive skills like critical thinking and problem-solving. Araujo et al. (2020) observe that while AI can streamline decision-making processes, over-dependence on AI risks dehumanizing education by removing the critical human element from instructional and administrative decisions.

Providing Performance-Based Activities

Mogavi et al. (2024) suggest that teachers can counteract over-reliance on ChatGPT by incorporating performance-based activities such as presentations and group projects into their lessons. These tasks require students to actively engage with the material, fostering deeper learning and critical thinking. Salendab (2021) agrees, noting that performance-based assessments encourage students to apply their knowledge in practical contexts, preparing them for success beyond the classroom. Herft (2023) adds that ChatGPT can be used to support these activities by generating prompts or helping students develop ideas, but it should not replace hands-on learning.

Being Responsible in Using Artificial Intelligence

Teachers have also emphasized the importance of responsible AI use. Baidoo-Anu and Owusu (2023) argue that students need clear guidelines on how to use ChatGPT ethically and effectively. Teachers must guide students in verifying AI-generated content and understanding the tool's limitations. By promoting responsible AI literacy, educators can help students balance the benefits of ChatGPT with the need to develop critical thinking and independent problem-solving skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research design in a multiple case approach to further understand the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights related to the particular phenomenon participants experienced. Qualitative research, as defined, does not require numerical data but instead focuses on syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic data to arrive at in-depth exploratory insights. This study employed interviews to collect, analyze, and discuss the data (Creswell, 1998).

Participants

The participants of the study include three (3) junior high school teachers, three (3) senior high school teachers, and (3) college teachers. These nine (9) participants were selected based on the criteria of the study, ensuring representation from each educational level. Each of the participants underwent in-depth interviews, with the researcher conducted individual interviews with them to gather their viewpoints and insights.

Instrument

To collect data for this study, the researcher followed a comprehensive protocol across pre-interview, interview, and post-interview phases. An interview guide was developed and validated by a panel of experts, ensuring alignment with the study's objectives. After validation, the researcher obtained an endorsement letter and sought consent from the adviser to proceed. Approval was then requested from the institution's administration to conduct face-to-face interviews with selected instructors and teachers.

Once approval was secured, participants were notified, and their consent was obtained through signed consent forms. The researcher provided a thorough orientation covering the purpose of the study, methodology, and participants' rights. All interviews were recorded with participants' permission, and confidentiality was strictly maintained. Recorded data were transcribed, reviewed by the participants, and then translated. To ensure data reliability, the interview guide was validated by a panel of experts, and member checking was used, allowing participants to review and verify their transcribed responses. After verification, data analysis was performed to derive meaningful insights for the study's conclusions and recommendations.

Procedure

The researcher initiated the study by drafting a formal permission letter to the institution's administration, where the research was to be conducted. After receiving approval from the panel, the researcher sent a letter requesting permission from the institution's administration to conduct the study with the identified instructors and teachers. Participants were informed through messages or email, and participation was based on their availability and willingness.

Each participant was given a consent form to sign, ensuring they understood their role in the study and their rights, including confidentiality and voluntary withdrawal at any stage. Prior to the interviews, an orientation was held to explain the study's objectives,

interview procedures, and participants' rights, including privacy and the recording of the session. All interview sessions were documented, and the researcher ensured that participants had the opportunity to review and confirm the accuracy of the transcriptions before proceeding with data analysis.

Data Analysis

A thematic analysis approach was employed to process and interpret the qualitative data collected from interviews. Following Creswell's (2009) proposed data analysis process, the researcher transcribed, translated, and systematically coded the participants' responses to facilitate thematic analysis within this case study. Thematic analysis, often referred to as coding, categorizes responses and identifies recurring themes to construct a structured representation of thematic concepts. These discernible themes offer valuable insights within the data, which can be further analyzed and interpreted.

Through systematic thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns, identifying recurring themes based on the obtained data (Dye, 2021). Throughout the analysis phase, the researcher relied on the transcripts and translated versions of the participants' responses. Using a systematic coding process, the researcher categorized and structured recurring responses to formulate an exhaustive thematic analysis. Concepts were then methodically arranged and assessed, considering their interrelationships, commonalities, and distinctions, with the support of a data analyst.

Ethical Considerations

According to Bhandari (2024), ethical principles serve as guidelines for ensuring research integrity and the protection of participants' rights. These principles help researchers conduct studies responsibly, safeguarding the well-being of individuals involved. Kalu and Bwalya (2017) emphasize that clear communication and informed consent are vital for building trust between researchers and participants, thereby avoiding ethical issues.

In this study, I adhered to ethical standards by ensuring participants' autonomy through clear communication and obtaining informed consent before conducting interviews. I maintained confidentiality by using pseudonyms and securely storing all data in password-protected files, in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participants were also given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Benevolence was upheld by conducting interviews in a safe and comfortable environment, ensuring that participants did not experience any harm, embarrassment, or judgment. Participants were provided the opportunity to ask questions or skip sensitive topics, maintaining their comfort throughout the process. Lastly, to ensure justice, participants were selected fairly based on appropriate criteria, and their contributions were acknowledged with tokens of appreciation. These ethical principles—respect for autonomy, confidentiality, benevolence, and justice—were consistently applied to ensure the protection and fair treatment of all participants.

Results and Discussion

A qualitative approach was used to answer questions about the participant's unique characteristics, perceptions, and insights. Using this cue, the researcher conducted a qualitative multiple-case study to collect data from the target respondents. It seeks to substantiate the claim that the case study technique, specifically the multiple-case studies design, can be used successfully to delve beneath the surface of a situation and provide a rich context for understanding the phenomena under investigation (Tomaszewski et al. 2020). There were three cases under investigation, each with a participant. The researcher interviewed the participant, and the results were analyzed per case.

Table 1. *Perceptions of Teachers in the Use of ChatGPT among the Students*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Absence of Academic Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Academic integrity, as I mentioned earlier, regarding that incident of copying and pasting. The academic integrity there is nowhere to be found, nothing at all. It is really gone because no one really knows where it came from." – IDI-01 • " They are very reliant there, dependent. You cannot really tell if the output is theirs. You cannot assess if it is their own work, it turns out it is just from ChatGPT. Especially during our modular time when they just submit their output, you would not know it is just from ChatGPT." – IDI-03 • "This really affects academic integrity. Why? Because when students copy and paste work, it is dishonest. They are not really learning because everything comes from the internet or apps like ChatGPT. So, academic integrity suffers because of it." – IDI-04 • "Similar to what I mentioned earlier, academic integrity and overall learning outcomes are indeed affected. Firstly, there is the issue of copy-pasting outputs, which undermines honesty and fails to properly attribute sources of information. This lack of academic integrity compromises the credibility of the work." – IDI-06 • "When it comes to the students' activities, it is like I cannot discern anymore. If their performance is high, it is difficult for me to identify – I will be puzzled if it was them who did it or someone else." – IDI-08

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| Potential Consequence of Promoting Students' Laziness | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "But, right now, when I check students' outputs, there are already doubts as to whether it is really coming from their own ideas or they just got an idea from ChatGPT." – IDI-09 • "Also, AI brings people laziness, people are really getting lazy now because they rely heavily, they are very dependent on AI." – IDI-01 • "There are transformations, they become lazy. They would just say, 'there is ChatGPT, I will just rely on it there.'" – IDI-02 • "For students, this is crucial because when there are tasks like essays, the easiest part is having it done. Even for research papers, you just give a title and you can have a finished paper." – IDI-07 • "Nowadays, students are very dependent because of this application. They do not put much effort because it is just one click away, they can have anything done instantly, even just a sentence." – IDI-08 • "However, the challenge is that we keep relying solely on that tool, and at the same time, students become lazy because the information they need is just one click away. They only need to instruct the AI or ChatGPT specifically if they want, and of course, AI will automatically provide the information or the thing they need." – IDI-09 |
| Contrast Between Traditional Method and Modern Method of Learning | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "They are not able to experience life compared to before like me who experienced how difficult it is to dive into the library. Now, it is easy for them to just type and the answer is generated right away." – IDI-01 • "Back then, we used to really go to the library, we would spend time there, we would read until we understood it. Now, for them, 'ChatGPT is the key'." – IDI-02 • "In the past, we only had the library and Google, that is all. But now, it is different, they do not even go to the library anymore, it is like it does not exist for them." – IDI-08 • "Before ChatGPT existed, I could see students really striving to improve or enhance their skills... trying to exert effort in searching for information in the library, Google, and even being aware that Wikipedia is not solely a correct source of information. But right now, because of the existence of ChatGPT, they no longer check whether the information is true and correct." – IDI-09 |
| Potential Consequence of Declining Critical Thinking Skills | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "For me, in junior high and senior high... it is probably okay in senior high if it is during research, but in junior high, for me, if they can stop it, that is my concern, they should stop because it really affects, especially critical thinking." – IDI-02 • "They do not think much, their critical thinking skills are not very good, they do not know how to analyze, for example, in math, if they encounter a problem, they just write the problem there, and if they cannot find the equation when they search, they just will not answer." – IDI-03 • "When students become too reliant, it significantly affects their performance and diminishes their ability to think critically and engage in metacognition. This notable transformation towards dependency is evident in their performances and behaviors, leading to a decline in their cognitive processing and critical thinking skills. Critical thinking should be enhanced because it allows us to assess how well students understand and analyze information." – IDI-04 • "Previously, before the advent of ChatGPT, I observed that students would exert effort and think independently. However, now with the presence of ChatGPT, completing assignments has become effortless for them. This easy accessibility lowers their performance and alters their thinking process." – IDI-05 • "My main concern is the learning of the students, especially their ability to think critically and solve problems on their own." – IDI-06 |
| Viewing ChatGPT as a Supplementary Tool | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Its main purpose is to support and provide additional information to deepen understanding. It is meant to supplement learning by offering what students may have missed in the lesson or what they haven't understood yet. ChatGPT is a tool to supplement their understanding, providing additional learning, resources, information, and ideas they are seeking. However, the problem arises when everything revolves around ChatGPT." – IDI-04 • "ChatGPT should only serve as a supplement, ideally. Its purpose should be supplementary to students' learning, but unfortunately, its usage has exceeded that purpose." – IDI-06 • "For me, it is actually helpful because to be honest, we are also using that platform. Essentially, it is supplementary, so it helps to enhance, it really helps, that is the main goal of ChatGPT. But, as for the teachers, it is okay because there are inputs there, information that you can put on slides, you have a lot of things you can do, and sometimes it also lessens the workload of the teacher because of ChatGPT." – IDI-07 • "And for the benefits of students using ChatGPT, it is helpful because accessing information is easy, and they can easily contribute ideas." – IDI-08 • "Students already rely on that tool but for me, when it first emerged, it was really helpful. Of course, it is a very big advantage for us to have this kind of AI since aside from enhancing how we can construct paragraphs, it really assists us in seeking other references which might be helpful for us to get the information that we need." – IDI-09 |

The Perceptions of Teachers in the Use of ChatGPT among the Students. At this point, After the retrieval of the data and analysis, it comes to an end that the teachers across various educational levels share common perceptions regarding their students' use of ChatGPT. It was found that the perceptions of teachers were absence of academic integrity, potential consequence of promoting students' laziness, contrast between traditional method and modern method of learning, Potential Consequence of declining critical thinking skills, viewing ChatGPT as a supplementary tool. These themes are supported by various related literature and theories.

Absence of Academic Integrity

The results indicate that teachers are concerned about the erosion of academic integrity due to the increasing reliance on ChatGPT. Participants reported instances of plagiarism and challenges in verifying the authenticity of students' work, aligning with concerns raised in other studies (Cotton et al., 2024; Rahman et al., 2023). The ability of ChatGPT to generate indistinguishable text from human writing exacerbates the difficulty in maintaining academic honesty. This theme underscores the need for educators to address the ethical implications of AI tools in the classroom.

Potential Consequence of Promoting Students' Laziness

Another significant theme was the potential for ChatGPT to promote laziness among students. Teachers observed that students often rely on ChatGPT for instant answers, reducing their motivation to engage with academic material. This over-reliance on AI mirrors findings from Iqbal et al. (2023) and Yilmaz and Karaoglan (2023), who noted that such dependence can diminish students' initiative and critical thinking skills. While ChatGPT provides convenience, it may inadvertently encourage passive learning.

Contrast Between Traditional Method and Modern Method of Learning

Teachers highlighted a clear distinction between traditional research methods and the modern reliance on tools like ChatGPT. Previously, students had to exert significant effort in gathering information, but now, the ease of AI-driven searches has shifted their approach to learning. This reflects the broader changes in education noted by Rahman and Watanobe (2023), who suggest that while AI offers advantages, it may limit students' ability to engage deeply with material, thereby affecting critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Potential Consequence of Declining Critical Thinking Skills

A recurrent concern among participants was the potential decline in students' critical thinking abilities due to the use of ChatGPT. Educators emphasized that students' reliance on AI could hinder their capacity to analyze and solve problems independently. Suriano et al. (2024) support this notion, arguing that while AI tools can assist with basic tasks, they may prevent students from developing higher-order thinking skills. The findings suggest the need for a balanced integration of AI in education to preserve critical thinking.

Viewing ChatGPT as a Supplementary Tool

Despite the concerns, teachers also acknowledged that ChatGPT has potential as a supplementary learning tool. When used responsibly, it can enhance understanding and provide additional resources for students. Studies by Crompton and Burke (2024) and Shouran (2023) highlight how AI tools like ChatGPT can offer valuable support, especially for students who need extra assistance. However, educators must guide students in using these tools appropriately to prevent over-reliance.

Table 2. Insights of Teachers in the Use of ChatGPT among the Students

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Providing Performance-based Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Perhaps we can explore ways to minimize the reliance of learners on technologies like ChatGPT. We can employ alternative methods and strategies such as utilizing performance-based approaches. Instead of solely focusing on written works like essays or creating paragraphs, we can steer away from them and opt for performance-based tasks. Collaborative approaches, brainstorming sessions, and other interactive methods can also be beneficial." – IDI-04 ● "We might want to avoid activities that are prone to the use of ChatGPT, particularly those that involve essay-type outputs or written assignments. Instead, we can design tasks that are performance-based or collaborative, where students work together to solve certain scenarios or challenges." – IDI-06 ● "The best approach is to avoid making activities into assignments, especially essays and sentence construction, during class activities. These activities should be done right there in the classroom to minimize the use of, of course, ChatGPT and prevent them from becoming overly dependent on it." – IDI-08 ● "Perhaps, we should not solely focus on giving tasks to students such as essays because they are prone to copying and pasting information from ChatGPT. Instead, we can opt for performance-based tasks where they will perform inside the class. This way, we can truly identify their performances and potentials. Utilizing performance-based tasks is a better option compared to traditional pen-and-paper tasks." – IDI-09
Being Responsible in Using Artificial Intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "I highly recommend using ChatGPT responsibly. Let us value the benefits and advantages it brings and use it properly to elevate and enhance our skills. Use it responsibly with balance, understanding that ChatGPT is meant to be supplemental. We can ask for assistance, but remember to be responsible in its usage." – IDI-04

- My recommendation is to know ChatGPT. Understand how to use it responsibly, recognize your limitations, and know when to rely solely on ChatGPT. Be aware of its dos and don'ts." – IDI-06
- "Even in using ChatGPT, it should be used properly, honestly, and productively. Properly means in moderation, just the right amount. Honestly means that if there is something to be done, do not solely depend on ChatGPT and do not just copy and paste everything." – IDI-07
- "I always tell them that we should not become dependent on ChatGPT, we should not rely solely on it for information because we have a lot of resources. Not only ChatGPT can help us, we have Google, Google Scholars that we can use for our research, for our assignments, and all." – IDI-08
- "It is just that, as teachers, we need to keep doing our part. Aside from reminding them, there is nothing wrong if you utilize this AI as long as we use it as a platform, as a springboard to create our own output or idea. We also need to control how we use the tool since it is only a tool." – IDI-09

Insights of Teachers in the Use of ChatGPT among their Students. After retrieving and analyzing the data gathered from the participants, it was revealed that the teachers have various insights regarding the use of ChatGPT among their students. The researcher identified two themes: providing performance-based activities and being responsible in using artificial intelligence.

Providing Performance-Based Activities

Teachers suggested that the reliance on AI tools like ChatGPT can be minimized by shifting towards performance-based tasks that actively engage students. They recommended activities such as presentations, group projects, and simulations, which encourage deeper learning and critical thinking. These activities help students apply their knowledge in practical, real-world contexts rather than relying on AI for answers. This insight aligns with Mogavi et al. (2024), who found that performance-based assessments prevent overreliance on AI and promote independent learning. Teachers emphasized that such approaches enhance essential skills like collaboration, communication, and problem-solving, preparing students for success beyond academic settings.

Being Responsible in Using Artificial Intelligence

Another key insight from teachers was the need for responsible use of AI tools. While AI offers numerous educational benefits, teachers stressed the importance of using it ethically and with proper understanding of its limitations. They encouraged students to balance AI use with independent learning, ensuring that ChatGPT is used as a supplementary resource rather than a replacement for critical thinking and problem-solving. This recommendation mirrors findings from Baidoo-Anu and Owusu (2023), who advocated for clear guidelines and open discussions around the ethical use of AI in education. Teachers in the study also emphasized the need for students to verify AI-generated content and critically evaluate its accuracy, promoting AI literacy and ethical responsibility.

Conclusions

Teachers' perspectives on ChatGPT underscore the need for balanced AI integration in education, fostering academic integrity, student engagement, and critical thinking. Educators are encouraged to promote AI literacy within the curriculum to ensure responsible and mindful usage. Implementing performance-based assessments and collaborative activities can also help reduce overreliance on AI, cultivating independent thinking and essential problem-solving skills.

Future research should explore mixed-methods approaches to assess ChatGPT's broader impacts on student performance, engagement, and satisfaction, offering insights for policies that support effective AI integration. As AI continues to influence educational practices, ongoing teacher training and adaptive strategies will be essential to align technological advancements with foundational educational principles.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Honey Lyn B. Poraso

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines